

Process of Human Value Inculcation and Role of Family, Society and Educational Institution

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This study examines the process of human value formation and the critical role that family, society, and educational institutions play in teaching values. Human values serve as guiding principles that shape ethical decisions and social behavior. Also this study examines the influence of family dynamics, including parental role modeling, communication, and emotional nurturance, on the transmission and internalization of values. It analyzes how societal factors such as cultural norms, religious teachings, and societal expectations affect the formation of values. In addition, the study examines the role of educational institutions in explicitly teaching and reinforcing values through curricula, character education programs, and interactions with teachers and peers. By analyzing the collective efforts of family, society, and educational institutions, this study aims to deepen our understanding of the processes through which individuals acquire and embrace ethical values, which ultimately contributes to the promotion of a responsible and harmonious society.

Keywords: Morals, Ethics, Values, Family, Society, Educational Institution.

Introduction : The process of formulating human values and communicating them to individuals is influenced by various social factors, including family, society, and educational institutions. Human values are guiding principles that shape an individual's moral compass, ethical choices, and social behavior. Understanding how these values are shaped and transmitted is critical to fostering a harmonious and responsible society.

As the primary socializing agent, the family plays a fundamental role in the transmission of values. Parents serve as primary role models by exemplifying ethical behavior and transmitting values through their actions and interactions with their children. The family environment, including communication patterns, emotional nurturing, and disciplinary practices, has significant influence on the transmission and internalization of values. Society as a whole also contributes to the formation of values. Cultural norms, religious teachings, and societal expectations shape individuals' understanding of what is right, wrong, important, or desirable. Through various social institutions and practices, society provides a framework for individuals to develop and adopt ethical values that are consistent with the broader social fabric. In addition, educational institutions play a critical role in explicitly teaching and reinforcing values. Schools, as formal educational institutions, have the opportunity to shape values through curriculum, character education programs, and interactions with teachers and peers. The educational environment provides a platform for students to learn and practice values such as respect, responsibility, empathy, and fairness.

The purpose of this study is to examine the intricate processes of human value formation and the role of family, society, and educational institutions in teaching values. By analyzing the influence of these social actors, this study will contribute to a deeper understanding of how individuals acquire and adopt ethical values. Ultimately, the results of this study can inform the development of policies and interventions that promote positive and

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responsible values education, leading to the development of individuals who contribute positively to society.

Objectives:

- To Study the process of evolution of Human Values
- To review the role of different stakeholders in inculcation of Human Values.

Research Methodology : This study is partly research and partly review article, first objective of the study is analytical in nature while second objective is explanatory in nature. On the basis of data this can be classified secondary study, a number of studies have been taken into consideration for generating a conclusion. One's view may differ from the conclusion generated here because this is a qualitative study based on the philosophical foundation.

Formulation of Human Values : Out of the 1.2 million identified species in the world being human is considered as a blessing because they have special qualities like high intelligence, their capacity for growth and change, most developed form of language and communication, creativity and imagination, Consciousness & Self- Awareness, emotional depth and many more. These qualities are not inherent or immediately created; these are the culmination of evolution held by the human interaction. These interactions can be classified by the Morals and Ethics based on Values. And further these morals are dictated by society, Culture or Religion while Ethics are personally determined for governing the persons own life. For understanding the process of value formulation we need proceed systematically from the origin:

Understanding Moral, Ethics and Values:

Morals: Morality or Moral is an individual's personal choice, behavior, principles or values about righteousness or wrongness about any particular Activity, thought or feelings. In other words we can say it is the personal judgment made by an Individual which may differs from person to person or culture to culture. What is morally wrong in one culture may be morally right. Morality is feels like imposed from outside but one may be morally right even if no justification is available or without any logical reasoning. It is sensitive to particular case based on gut instinct. It is subjective in nature.

Ethics: It is the code of conduct or set of rules which is not flexible in any particular case, based on logical reasoning which tends to be more objective than moral. Ethics are universal which applies to groups and organizations. It guides us how to act but morality is about how to behave in a particular situation. In other words ethics can be defined as a formal set of beliefs or professional code of conduct termed as rule based on which the organization or the group of Individual will act in manner so as to achieve the pre-defined code of conduct.

Ethics and Morality : Ethics decides whether your actions are wrong or right but morality decides whether your intentions are good or bad. Ethics and morality are not different; the base of ethics is based on morality. Generally acceptable case of morality is ethics, based on this general acceptance one sets his rules to guide the actions of his personal life which is called as ethics. Suppose there is a case of euthanasia, for a doctor using this drug is ethically wrong because this may be misused, but there is a patient whose chances of being alive is negligible but he is in intolerable pain. In this case the doctor is morally right.

Values: Values are the collective conceptions of what is considered good, desirable, proper, bad and improper in a culture formulated through a complex evolution of morals and ethics. We may say socially or culturally desirable characteristics are known as good human values such as love, patience, honesty, reliability, non-violence which are non desirable known as bad values such as dishonesty, impatience, hate, violence. It is the result of the experience

since a long time which has classified the values good or bad. And the term set of rules known as ethics and a set righteousness and wrongness known as morality are determined by the fundamental principles adopted by the Individual or organizations known as values. If a person values non-violence he or she will try to avoid violence even if the person with who is an argument is wrong. If someone values truth he will never lie even if in short term it may be harmful for him because he knows in long term telling truth is beneficial.

Process of Human Value Formulation : In the previous section we have seen the definition of human values, morals and ethics with examples. Now the question is how the human values are formulated? The development of human civilization and the concepts of morality and values are closely related. As civilizations have evolved and progressed, so have the understanding and formulation of moral principles and values.

Religious and Philosophical Traditions: The emergence of the major world religions, including Judaism, Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, and Buddhism, played an important role in the formation of morals and values. These religions provided moral frameworks and ethical guidelines by emphasizing virtues, moral duties, and principles of proper behavior. Philosophical traditions, such as those of the ancient Greek philosophers Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle, explored concepts of virtue, ethics, and the pursuit of a good life. Their ideas influenced later ethical thought and contributed to the formulation of moral values.

Social and Legal Systems: As human civilizations became more complex, social and legal systems emerged to regulate human behavior. These systems contained moral and ethical principles to maintain order, resolve conflict, and promote justice.

Cultural and Societal Shifts: The development of human civilization has been accompanied by cultural and social changes that affect moral values. As societies change, so do the norms and values they uphold. Cultural diversity and cross-cultural exchange have impacted the formulation of moral values as societies interact and adopt different perspectives and ethical frameworks. Social movements such as the civil rights movement, the women's movement, and the environmental movement have challenged existing moral norms and advocated for greater equality, justice, and ethical responsibility.

Scholars, philosophers, and ethicists have engaged in ethical reflection and intellectual discourse that has further shaped concepts of morality and values. Ethical theories such as consequentialism, deontology, virtue ethics, and feminist ethics have emerged from these deliberations and provide a framework for ethical analysis and decision-making.

Inculcation of Human Values and Role of different Stakeholders : Human civilization has served as a backdrop for the development, transmission, and transformation of moral values. The interplay of cultural, religious, philosophical, and social factors has played a crucial role in the ongoing formulation and development of morality and values throughout history. Values in the narrower sense are what is good, desirable, or worth striving for. Values are the motivation for purposeful action, they are the goals by which we act, and they can take many forms. Personal values are personal beliefs about right and wrong and may or may not be considered moral, while cultural values are adopted by religions or societies and reflect what is important in the particular context.

On the basis of acquisition values can:

Innate- Values due to our Genes and Conscience.

Acquired- Values due to social institution and influences.

On the basis of desirability it can be:

Positive or Desirable- such as honesty, reliability, truthful etc.

Negative of Undesirable- Dishonest, Violence, etc.

Some values can be negative as well as positive depending upon the time and situation such being flexible or strict could be both desirable and non-desirable both depending upon the situation.

Role of Family in inculcating Human Values: The family is the most important platform and foundation for a child to learn values. It is the first group of individuals with whom one comes into contact. Children identify with their parents and other family members and make them their personal role models by imitating and imitating them. Social norms and customs established by the family provide the emotional and physical foundation for a child. They lead to a disciplined and organized life. The family prepares the individual for the real world and equips him with everything he needs to succeed in society. A child with a good sense of right and wrong is less likely to fall victim to deviant influences. Values such as kindness, love, compassion, respect, tolerance, etc. can be instilled through family values. A poor family experience can seriously hinder the development of a person's moral and intellectual capacities. The family, as the primary and most important instance of socialization, sets the pattern for the child's outlook. It encourages the child's intellectual development and supports his aspirations and reasonable values.

Some of the values and ways that facilitate the child's growing up in a highly harmonious environment are taught by the family in an informal way.

- Love, compassion, self-sacrifice, and values of sharing and caring develop implicitly in a child.
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- Praise and encourage discovery.
- Children observe and acquire values unconsciously. When they observe the mother cooking and taking care of the whole family, values such as compassion are taught. When female members in the family are treated with respect, respect for women is instilled in the child.
- Set realistic goals for them.
- Act as a role model yourself.
- Sensitizes youth to weaker and marginalized groups.
- Prohibits dishonest acts.
- Helps youth develop a sense of distinction between right and wrong so they can develop their own judgment.

Parenting Styles of Values and their outcomes:

1. Authoritative Style- The authoritarian style of parenting assumes that their children have a limited level of autonomy and that the value system is imposed upon them. This can lead to a lack of empathy, bias, and self-centered behavior.
2. Democratic Styles- By using a democratic approach to dealing with their children, it aims to deal with them rationally and issue-oriented, while also providing positive reinforcements when a child displays an appropriate behavior. Children of this type display a high degree of objectiveness, impartiality, tolerance, and patience, among other characteristics.
3. Permissive Styles- Neglect, apathy, and non-involvement are characterized by the permissive style. Negative values can be developed by children and can be directed to socially non-desirable directions.

Role of Society in inculcating Human Values:

Role of Educational Institution in inculcating Human Values: Education is an effective and all-encompassing phenomenon for individual development and social change. A balanced development of mind and body in harmony with the strengthening of human personality through values-based education to reach higher levels of consciousness. Since ancient times, value education has been manifested and upheld in society through the Vedas, Upanishads, epics, Buddhist moral code, etc. Morality, honesty, duty, brotherhood, friendship, etc. became more and more important.

Education plays an important role in improving values.

- Science encourages rational thinking and questioning of outdated beliefs,
- Literature helps us understand human nature and the prevailing social values of a particular era,
- An account of the lives of great leaders like Gandhi's Train Journey to Pretoria shows how he stood up against injustice.
- The content of a textbook plays an important role in teaching values.
- In the classroom, important values are also taught through stories, e.g., a lesson about Hellen Keller teaches the importance of remaining persistent and determined despite adversity

Teachers are the role models of students in schools and play an important role in teaching ethical behavior to students.

- Values such as teamwork, leadership, etc. are taught.
- Gokhale was a political guru of Gandhi and in many ways shaped Gandhi's ideology and attitude towards India and life.
- When a teacher advertises his tutoring services during formal classes in school, he indirectly conveys materialistic content.
- A child who has been excessively punished by the teacher will develop a wrong attitude.

Findings and Conclusions: The process of human value education involves the transmission and internalization of values through cultural and social influences, personal experience, moral development, and cognitive processes. It is shaped by interactions with family, society, and educational institutions and leads to the formation of an individual's moral compass that guides his or her behavior in various contexts. Family, society, and educational institutions play a crucial role in the transmission of human values. The family serves as the primary socialization agent, modeling and reinforcing values through role models, communication, and emotional care. Society as a whole influences values through cultural norms, religious teachings, and societal expectations. Educational institutions provide formal educational and character development programs in which values are explicitly taught and reinforced. Schools create environments in which students practice and internalize values through interactions with teachers and peers. Together, these institutions shape individuals' moral development, guide their ethical choices, and promote the values necessary for a harmonious and responsible society.

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